

COT - BASED CHALLENGES OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: BASIS FOR RESKILLING AND UPSKILLING PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the upskilling and reskilling needs of public elementary school teachers in Panglao District, Division of Bohol, as a basis for designing a responsive professional development program. Anchored on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and the Classroom Observation Tool (COT), the research employed a qualitative descriptive–exploratory design using semi-structured interviews with 21 selected teachers across different grade levels. Findings revealed that most teachers are in the early to mid-career stage, with adequate foundational competencies but limited mentorship from highly experienced educators. While teachers demonstrated proficiency in content knowledge, lesson planning, instructional resources, and assessment practices, significant pedagogical challenges were identified. These include difficulties in integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), managing interactive and learner-centered classroom environments, applying varied literacy and numeracy strategies, and implementing differentiated instruction to address diverse learner needs. Teachers adopted adaptive strategies such as scaffolded questioning, collaborative learning, and flexible grouping, supported by technical assistance from school heads through pre- and post-conference feedback. However, a gap between training and actual classroom implementation persists. The study concludes that a structured, competency-based reskilling and upskilling program, supported by continuous mentoring, coaching, and contextualized training, is essential to enhance instructional practices, improve classroom observation performance, and achieve better learner outcomes.

Keywords: *upskilling, reskilling, Classroom Observation Tool (COT), Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), differentiated instruction, teacher professional development, learner-centered teaching, instructional challenges, elementary education*

INTRODUCTION

Public school elementary teachers play an important role in shaping the learning foundation of children. As curriculum standards continue to change, technology advances rapidly, and classrooms become more diverse, the professional development of teachers is significant to maintaining quality education. To actively address these challenges of the 21st century, teachers must continuously update their knowledge and skills. This makes upskilling and reskilling essential not only to keep up with modern teaching practices but also to meet the varied needs of learners and support their overall professional growth.

Research shows that teachers' professional development is essential. Postholm (2018) explains that it brings positive changes in classroom practice and improves student learning. Through continuous training, workshops, and further studies, teachers are able to update their knowledge, adopt new teaching methods, and improve classroom management strategies. This allows them to create more engaging, inclusive, effective learning environments and leads to better student learning outcomes.

Ulla (2018) also highlights that action research and classroom action plans can improve teachers' practices and professional growth. As teachers grow professionally, they become more confident and equipped to address 21st century challenges. Since education keeps changing with new methods, technologies, and curriculum standards, professional development is crucial. It ensures that teachers remain effective, proving that quality teachers lead to quality education.

In response, the Department of Education (DepEd) introduced various professional development initiatives designed to enhance teacher competencies. Central to these initiatives is the enhancement of In-Service Training (INSET) programs, which are designed to the advancement of teachers' professional development. Moreover, DepEd Order No. 11, s. 2019, for instance, sought to strengthen professional development by restructuring the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP). This reform established a more coherent and systematic approach to capacity-building programs, addressing long-standing issues of fragmented and inconsistent training delivery. Furthermore, DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, institutionalized personal growth and professional development as one of the core domains in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Within this domain, particular emphasis is placed on the demonstration of "professional reflection and learning to improve practice" as well as the pursuit of clearly defined "professional development goals" (DepEd, 2017, p. 24).

The successful implementation of professional development initiatives is not without its challenges particularly in ensuring that professional development programs are fully aligned with the actual upskilling and reskilling needs of teachers. Initial pilot runs have revealed that many of these programs remain centralized and traditional, which offer limits their flexibility and responsiveness to the dynamic needs of educators (Ovens, 2005). Recent findings by Rivera et al. (2025) reveal that only 17% of public-school teachers participated in relevant training during the school year 2023–2024, with a notably high non-participation rate, particularly in Metro Manila.

In the Division of Bohol, specifically Panglao District, only 28% or 49 teachers out of 176 Elementary teachers participated the Deped's Expanded Career Progression (ECP) System for the reason of disqualification due to lack of relevant trainings and seminars. Teachers are required to have acquired relevant trainings and professional development activities that aligned with Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and should be National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) accredited for teachers to gain credit.

Alignment is essential, as training that directly responds to teachers' contextual realities equips them with practical skills that can be immediately applied in classroom practice. Ensuring that professional development initiatives are responsive, relevant, and effectively tailored to teachers' needs is therefore critical in addressing the demands of contemporary education.

Hence, the research sought to assess the upskilling and reskilling needs of public-school elementary teachers as a basis for designing a professional development program. By focusing on teachers' needs in managing curriculum overload, diverse learners and navigating new teaching platforms, this research aims to contribute to the improvement of the education sector and identify the skills and competencies that teachers need to acquire to address the challenges and improve the quality of education. The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide insights into how professional development programs can be designed to address specific, contextual challenges in a way that promotes both teacher growth and student success.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the upskilling and reskilling needs of public elementary school teachers of Panglao District for the school year 2025-2026 as basis for designing a professional development program.

Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the teacher's profile in terms of:
 - 1.1 length of service;
 - 1.2 current grade level handled; and
 - 1.3 latest trainings and seminars attended?

2. What are the challenges perceived by teachers based on PPST domains?
3. What are the adaptive measures to address the challenges?
4. What are the technical supports by administrator, school head/principal?
5. What work action plan on reskilling and upskilling needs of teachers can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically a descriptive–exploratory approach, to examine the Classroom Observation Tool (COT)-based challenges experienced by public elementary school teachers and to use these insights as bases for the development of a reskilling and upskilling program. Qualitative research was appropriate for this study as it allowed for an in-depth exploration of teachers’ lived experiences, perceptions, and meanings attached to classroom observations and professional development processes.

The qualitative design was anchored in an interpretivist paradigm, which assumed that reality was socially constructed and best understood through the perspectives of those directly involved. In the context of this study, the interpretivist approach enabled the researcher to capture the nuanced experiences of teachers as they navigated COT implementation, performance expectations, feedback mechanisms, and professional learning opportunities. This design was particularly suited to uncovering contextual factors, institutional practices, and personal interpretations that quantitative measures may not have adequately captured.

Research Environment

The research was conducted among 12 public elementary schools situated within Panglao district under the administrative jurisdiction of the Schools Division of Bohol, geographically positioned within the First Congressional District of the Province of Bohol. These schools included Panglao Central Elementary School, Balicasag Elementary School, Panglao Central East Elementary School, Doljo Elementary School, Bil-isan Elementary School, Looc Elementary School, Tangnan Elementary School, Lourdes Elementary School, Libaong Elementary School, Tawala Elementary School, Bolod Elementary School, and Danao Elementary School.

These schools were considered appropriate for the study as public elementary school teachers in this setting regularly underwent classroom observations aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and participated in In-Service Training for Teachers (INSET) and other professional development activities mandated by the Department of Education and accredited by the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP). The selected schools provided a relevant context for examining

teachers' actual experiences, challenges, and professional learning needs related to COT implementation.

Research Participants

The population of the study consisted of selected public elementary school teachers in the district of Panglao. To ensure fair representation, the researcher employed a stratified random sampling technique, categorizing teachers by grade level (primary and intermediate), years of teaching experience, and subject specialization.

A sample size of 21 teachers was determined using established sampling formulas to ensure reliability and representativeness. The primary respondents were full-time public elementary school teachers in Panglao with at least one year of teaching experience to ensure adequate exposure to professional training and actual classroom instruction. Teachers from different grade levels and with varying teaching experiences were included to capture diverse perspectives.

Elementary teachers from private schools were excluded, as they follow different classroom observation tools and do not routinely undergo observations aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Additionally, non-teaching personnel and teachers with less than one year of experience were excluded. The table below presents the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Name of Schools	Grade level							No. of Teachers
	K	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	
Panglao CES	✓					✓		2
Balicasag ES			✓					1
Panglao Central East ES		✓		✓				2
Doljo ES		✓		✓	✓			3
Bil-isan ES						✓	✓	2
Looc ES				✓	✓			2
Tangnan ES		✓			✓			2
Lourdes ES	✓						✓	2
Libaong ES	✓					✓		2
Bolod ES			✓					1
Tawala ES							✓	1
Danao ES			✓					1
TOTAL								21

Research Instrument

To gather comprehensive data on the upskilling and reskilling needs of public elementary school teachers, the researcher employed a semi-structured interview. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected public elementary school teachers to elicit detailed accounts of their experiences with COT implementation. An interview guide was developed based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, and relevant professional development policies. The semi-structured format allowed flexibility for probing and follow-up questions, enabling participants to elaborate on specific challenges related to lesson preparation, classroom management, instructional strategies, assessment practices, and post-observation feedback.

Research Procedure

The researcher prepared all necessary documents, including the interview guide, informed consent form, and permission letters. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the school division superintendent, after which the researcher coordinated with the district supervisor and school principals to schedule interviews with selected teachers who provided consent.

Semi-structured interviews were personally administered using the validated interview guide, either face-to-face or via phone/virtual meeting if participants were unavailable. Each session lasted 10–15 minutes and began with an explanation of the study's purpose, participants' rights, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. With participants' approval, interviews were audio-recorded and supplemented with field notes to capture non-verbal cues.

Recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim, reviewed for accuracy, and assigned participant codes to ensure anonymity. Data were securely stored in password-protected digital folders accessible only to the researcher. Selected participants reviewed their transcripts for accuracy, and necessary corrections were incorporated. These procedures ensured ethical compliance, credibility, and trustworthiness of the qualitative data, providing a foundation for identifying COT-related challenges and informing the development of a reskilling and upskilling program.

RESULTS

The data were coded and categorized thematically using a qualitative lens, supported by frequency counts to show thematic saturation.

Table 2. Teacher's Profile in Terms of Years of Teaching Experience

Range of Years in Service	Number of Teachers (f)	Percentage (%)
1 – 5 years	7	33%
6 – 10 years	9	43%
11 – 15 years	2	10%
16 – 20 years	3	14%
21 years and above	0	0
Total	21	100%

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents are in the mid-career stage, with nine teachers (43%) having six to ten years of teaching experience. This is followed by seven teachers (33%) with one to five years of experience, while only a small proportion falls within the more experienced categories, with two teachers (10%) having eleven to fifteen years and three teachers (14%) having sixteen to twenty years of service. No respondents have more than twenty years of experience.

This distribution indicates that the teaching workforce is largely composed of early to mid-career educators. Teachers with fewer years of experience may still be developing essential competencies in classroom management, instructional delivery, and the application of varied teaching strategies, which may influence their ability to meet COT indicators. Meanwhile, mid-career teachers tend to demonstrate greater instructional stability but may still encounter challenges in adapting to evolving pedagogical approaches and diverse learner needs. More experienced teachers, although proficient in routine instructional practices, may face difficulties in integrating innovative and updated teaching strategies aligned with current educational reforms.

The differences in teaching experience suggest varying levels of readiness and challenges in implementing COT-based practices, highlighting the need for targeted professional development across career stages to enhance teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes. This finding is supported by Kini and Podolsky (2016), who found that teaching experience significantly improves instructional effectiveness, particularly in the early and mid-career stages. Similarly, Kraft et al. (2018) emphasized that continuous professional development is essential in sustaining teacher effectiveness across different stages of the teaching career.

Table 3. Number of Teacher's Profile per Grade level

Grade Level Taught	Number of Teachers
Kindergarten	3
Grade 1	3

Grade 2	3
Grade 3	3
Grade 4	3
Grade 5	3
Grade 6	3
Total	21

Table 3 shows that the teacher-participants were equally distributed across grade levels. This equal representation ensures balanced data collection and allows for fair comparison of COT-based challenges across different grade levels taught. With an equal number of teacher-participants per grade level, the study can more accurately determine whether the challenges identified through the Classroom Observation Tool are influenced by the nature of the grade level taught rather than unequal sample size. This strengthens the validity of the findings, as differences in challenges can be attributed to instructional demands and learner characteristics inherent to each grade level.

Furthermore, equal representation supports reliable analysis of COT indicators such as classroom management, differentiated instruction, learner engagement, and assessment strategies. It enables the study to identify grade-level specific patterns of strengths and difficulties, which might otherwise be overlooked if one grade level were overrepresented.

This balanced approach is also essential in developing an effective reskilling and upskilling program. When challenges are clearly identified across all grade levels, professional development interventions can be designed to address both common and grade-specific needs. As a result, the proposed program becomes more inclusive, equitable, and responsive to the diverse instructional contexts of public elementary school teachers.

In summary, having the same number of teachers handling different grade levels enhances the credibility of the study and ensures that its recommendations for professional development are grounded in comprehensive and balanced evidence.

Table 4. Teacher’s Profile in Terms of Latest Seminars and Trainings Attended

Title of Training/Seminar	Number of Teachers (f)	Percentage (%)	Focus Area/Relevance to COT
Mass Training of Teachers on the Revised K to 12 Curriculum	3	14%	Foundational Skills and Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Approaches, Classroom Environment and Management, and Assessment and Curriculum Planning
	6	29%	Catering to varied learner abilities

Upskilling of Key stage 2 teachers on the conduct of effective remediation			And Monitoring and evaluating learner progress
Upskilling of Key stage 1 teachers on the conduct of effective remediation	12	57%	Catering to varied learner abilities Monitoring and evaluating learner progress

Table 4 presents the teachers' profile in terms of the latest seminars and trainings attended. The data show that twelve teachers (57%) participated in the upskilling of Key Stage 1 teachers on effective remediation, six teachers (29%) attended the upskilling for Key Stage 2, and only three teachers (14%) joined the mass training on the Revised K to 12 Curriculum. This indicates that most teachers were recently engaged in specialized training focused on remediation and learner progress.

The findings further suggest a progressive sequence of professional development, where teachers initially underwent curriculum-based training before participating in more focused upskilling programs. This implies that teachers were first equipped with foundational competencies aligned with the K to 12 curriculum and later trained to address specific instructional challenges, particularly in catering to diverse learners and monitoring student performance—key areas assessed in the Classroom Observation Tool (COT).

However, the continued emphasis on remediation training indicates that challenges in implementing COT indicators persist despite prior exposure to comprehensive curriculum training. This suggests that while teachers may possess the necessary theoretical knowledge, difficulties remain in translating these competencies into consistent classroom practice. It also highlights that one-time, large-scale trainings may be insufficient to ensure mastery of complex instructional skills.

Overall, the results underscore the need for sustained, targeted, and practice-oriented professional development programs that bridge the gap between training and actual classroom implementation, thereby enhancing teachers' effectiveness in meeting COT standards. This finding is supported by Parojenog and Pabalan (2024), who emphasized that continuous and structured professional development is essential in improving teaching quality and educational standards. Similarly, Desimone and Garet (2015) highlighted that sustained and content-focused training significantly enhances teachers' instructional practices and student outcomes.

Table 5. Teacher’s COT-Based Challenges Based on PPST Domains

COT Indicator	Grade Level																					
	K			1			2			3			4			5			6			
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	
Indicator 1 Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas																						
Indicator 2 Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills					/					/						/						
Indicator 3 Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.				/		/	/		/				/			/	/		/			
Indicator 4 Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	/		/						/						/							/
Indicator 5 Manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.												/	/									
Indicator 6 Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners’ gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.		/		/																/		
Indicator 7 Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.																						
Indicator 8 Selecting, developing, organizing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT																						
Indicator 9 Designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative and summative assessments strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.																						

Table 5 presents the COT-based challenges of teachers across grade levels anchored on selected PPST indicators. The results show that no challenges were identified in Indicators 1, 7, 8, and 9, indicating that teachers generally demonstrate competence in content knowledge, lesson sequencing, use of instructional resources (including ICT), and assessment practices. This suggests that foundational teaching competencies are well-established among the respondents.

However, challenges are evident in selected pedagogical indicators. Indicator 2 reveals that some teachers experience difficulty in using varied teaching strategies to enhance learners' literacy and numeracy skills, suggesting limitations in applying diverse and effective instructional approaches. Indicator 3 shows the most frequent challenges across grade levels, indicating that developing critical, creative, and higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) is the most difficult area for teachers. This implies that many teachers still rely on traditional strategies and may need further support in designing activities that promote deeper learning.

Similarly, Indicator 4 highlights challenges in managing classroom structures that promote active engagement through exploration and hands-on activities, which may be influenced by constraints such as large class sizes, limited space, and preparation demands. Indicators 5 and 6 show minimal challenges, suggesting that most teachers are competent in behavior management and differentiated instruction, although a few still encounter difficulties in addressing diverse learner needs.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers are generally strong in content and planning-related competencies but face greater challenges in implementing learner-centered and higher-order thinking strategies. This underscores the need for targeted professional development focusing on instructional strategies, differentiation, and HOTS integration aligned with COT and PPST standards. This finding is supported by Parojenog and Pabalan (2024), who emphasized that improving teaching quality requires strengthening instructional practices beyond content knowledge. Similarly, Hattie et al. (2016) highlighted that effective teaching strategies, particularly those promoting higher-order thinking, have a significant impact on student learning outcomes.

Table 6. Teacher's COT Challenges Based on PPST Domains

No.	Responses	Theme Cluster	Emergent Theme (Challenges)
Participant 3	"I find indicator number 3, difficult for me which is all about applied a range of teaching strategies to develop creative thinking as well as higher-order thinking skills."	Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop creative thinking as well as higher-order thinking skills.	Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)
Participant 7	"The most challenging indicator, for me, using varied strategies that promote higher-order thinking skills. It's hard to attained because of limited time."	Using varied strategies that promote higher-order thinking skills.	Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)

Participant 10	<p>"I feel challenged in applying range of teaching strategies to develop critical, creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills."</p>	<p>Applying range of teaching strategies to develop critical, creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.</p>	<p>Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)</p>
Participant 18	<p>"Challenging...indicators related to learner engagement and higher-order thinking skills are the most challenging to me."</p>	<p>Related to learner engagement and higher-order thinking skills are the most challenging.</p>	<p>Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)</p>
Participant 19	<p>"For me, indicator 3 is the most challenging coz you need to applied strategies that develop creative and critical thinking, also higher-order thinking skills.</p>	<p>Applied strategies that develop creative and critical thinking, also higher-order thinking skills.</p>	<p>Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)</p>
Participant 1	<p>"I think kadtung na belong sa domain 1, sakop cya sa content knowledge and pedagogy. We are going to, kung at ato cyang tanawon, naghisgot tu cya about the use of range teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills. Mao tu cya challenging kaayo tu cya nako."</p>	<p>Range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.</p>	<p>Inconsistent Use of Varied Literacy and Numeracy Strategies</p>
Participant 16	<p>"Ang pinaka-challenge for me being a teacher in lower grades is that, applying more teaching ways that enhance learner in literacy and numeracy skills. Challenge for me</p>	<p>Applying more teaching ways that enhance learner in literacy and numeracy skills.</p>	<p>Inconsistent Use of Varied Literacy and Numeracy Strategies</p>

	because I need to focus one aspect at a time.”		
Participant 2	“In my case, the COT indicator related to classroom management and learner engagement are the most challenging to demonstrate during classroom observation.”	Classroom management	Managing and Interactive Spaces Structure Creating Learning
Participant 4	“Para naho, challenge kaau ang pag-manage sa mga bata inside the classroom during classroom observation. In fact, we need to ask their help during observations, but in reality, their attentions are unmanageable. Most of them feeling entitled.”	Managing learners during classroom observation is a challenge because of their unmanageable attentions.	Managing and Interactive Spaces Structure Creating Learning
Participant 8	“One I consider is using varied strategies that is suited to the diverse learners. So, there are what we call the fast learner and the slow learners, so you have to give different strategies so that we can meet up the objective for that particular day.”	Using varied strategies that is suited to the diverse learners	Practical Challenges in Differentiated Instruction
Participant 14	“The most challenging to me talks all about differentiated learning experiences. It is challenging as it requires tailoring instruction within limited class time. I have 44 learners in class and learner’s engagement is not a walk in the park.”	All about differentiated learning experiences.	Practical Challenges in Differentiated Instruction

Table 6 presents the most challenging indicator during classroom observations and a concise overview of the adaptive measures to address the Classroom observation challenges, which is a significant part in developing teachers. The table categorizes these challenges with the adaptive measures into thematic cluster, emergent themes, and associated codes.

Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS). The theme “*Difficulty in Integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS)*” highlights teachers’ struggles in facilitating learning experiences that require learners to analyze, evaluate, and create rather than merely remember and understand concepts. Higher-order thinking skills, grounded in Bloom’s Taxonomy, emphasize cognitive processes such as critical thinking, problem-solving, reasoning, and creativity. These competencies are strongly embedded in the goals of the Department of Education through the K to 12 Curriculum, which advocates learner-centered and inquiry-based instruction.

The identification of HOTS integration as the greatest challenge during classroom observations suggests that teachers may struggle to construct questions, activities, and assessments that align with higher cognitive domains. Integrating HOTS is closely tied to designing performance-based and authentic assessments and developing it often demands extended discussion and collaborative tasks. During classroom observations, teachers may prioritize completing content requirements over facilitating deep processing due to time constraints. Also, teachers may perceive learners as lacking foundational skills necessary for higher-order tasks especially in a heterogeneous class.

The difficulty in integrating higher-order thinking skills is not merely an instructional weakness but a systematic professional development need. Since HOTS is central to 21st century learning competencies, addressing this challenge through structured mentoring, collaborative lesson study, and targeted training workshops can directly improve instructional quality and learner outcomes.

Inconsistent Use of Varied Literacy and Numeracy Strategies. The emergent theme “*Inconsistent Use of Varied Literacy and Numeracy Strategies*” refers to the irregular or limited application of diverse instructional approaches aimed at developing learners’ reading, writing, comprehension, and mathematical skills during classroom observations. While teachers may demonstrate knowledge of literacy and numeracy instruction, the strategies employed were often repetitive, teacher-centered, or not sufficiently differentiated to address learners’ varied needs.

This theme surfaced during Classroom Observation tool (COT) implementation, where effective integration of literacy and numeracy strategies is expected to align with learner-centered, developmentally appropriate, and interactive teaching practices under the standards of the Department of Education and the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.

The inconsistent use of strategies may indicate a need for stronger pedagogical content knowledge in literacy and numeracy. Teachers might understand what to teach but require further upskilling in how to teach it effectively using varied, researched-based strategies. This aligns with broader thrust of strengthening foundational skills in response to national literacy and numeracy concerns.

Managing Structure and Creating Interactive Learning Space. The emergent theme “*Managing Structure and Creating Interactive Learning Space*” refers to teachers’ challenges in organizing the classroom environment and structuring learning experiences in ways that actively engage learners individually and collaboratively during classroom observations. This theme reflects difficulties in establishing clear routines and transitions, organizing physical and instructional space effectively and ensuring active learner participation.

This theme strongly connects with classroom observation indicators that emphasize learner engagement and meaningful exploration. The challenge indicates that while teachers may understand curriculum content, structuring dynamic and interactive learning environments remains an area for professional growth.

The emergence of this theme as a challenge underscores the evolving demands of modern pedagogy. Effective classroom environments require intentional organization, facilitative leadership, and adaptive instructional strategies. Addressing this through sustained professional development will enhance teacher competence, improve learner engagement, and strengthen overall instructional quality.

Practical Challenges in Differentiated Instruction. This emergent theme refers to the difficulties’ teachers experience in adjusting instructional strategies, materials, assessment tasks, and learning processes to accommodate learners’ diverse readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles during classroom observations. Teachers are expected to respond effectively to learner diversity. However, the emergence of this theme indicates that while teachers recognize its importance, practical implementation during classroom observations remains challenging.

Many teachers may understand the concept of differentiated instruction from trainings and seminars. However, translating theory into structured, observable classroom practices requires preparation of varied instructional materials, advanced lesson planning and time-efficient classroom management. Teachers need support in designing tiered lesson plans and differentiation must be embedded systematically. Also, coaching and modelling are necessary for sustainable implementation.

This theme underscores the evolving demands of inclusive education. While teachers recognize learner diversity, effective differentiation requires strategic planning, structured classroom management, adequate resources and sustained professional development. Addressing this through systematic reskilling and upskilling initiatives will enhance instructional responsiveness, promote equitable learning opportunities, and improve overall classroom effectiveness.

Adaptive Measures of Teachers to Address the Challenges during Classroom Observation. Teachers employed various adaptive measures to address challenges encountered during classroom observations. These adaptive practices were implemented particularly in response to difficulties in integrating higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), applying differentiated instruction, managing classroom structure, and utilizing varied literacy and numeracy strategies.

Teachers reported adjusting their instructional delivery by incorporating scaffolded questioning techniques, contextualized examples, collaborative learning strategies, and flexible grouping. Some participants emphasized revising lesson plans to better align with learners' readiness levels, while others highlighted the reorganization of classroom space to facilitate interactive and hands-on activities.

Furthermore, teachers demonstrated responsiveness to feedback provided by school heads. Post observation conferences served as opportunities for reflective practice, allowing teachers to identify areas for improvement and implement corrective strategies.

The data further indicated that adaptive measures were often influenced by technical assistance and professional development activities, including feedbacking, pre- and post-conference, seminars and curriculum training aligned with the standards set by the Department of Education.

Adaptive measures are essential in transforming classroom observation from a compliance-based activity into a growth-oriented professional practice. They empower teachers to address instructional gaps, improve classroom management, implement differentiated strategies, and align with curriculum reforms. More importantly, adaptive practices contribute to sustainable teacher development and improved student learning outcomes.

Technical Supports of Teachers by School Administrators/School Head in the Implementation of Classroom Observation. Technical support provided by school administrators or the school head during classroom observations is a key factor in enhancing teaching effectiveness, teacher confidence, and overall classroom quality. This support includes: Pre-conference, post-conference and feedbacking.

Teachers reported that guidance from the school head before classroom observations helped them prepare their lessons more effectively. This included clarifying observation criteria, reviewing lesson plans, and discussing instructional objectives. Such support was crucial in aligning teaching strategies with curriculum standards, reducing teacher anxiety, resulting in increased confidence during observations, and encouraging strategic lesson planning for better learner engagement.

Pre-conference technical support fosters a collaborative and developmental environment. Teachers perceive observations not as evaluative pressure but as an opportunity for growth and improvement. This support is important because it helps teachers align their instruction with curriculum standards and school priorities. Also, it reduces teacher anxiety during observations and it fosters a more confident teaching approach. Lastly, it ensures that teachers are aware of the criteria for evaluation, allowing them to strategically plan their lessons for optimal student engagement.

Technical support is most evident during post-conference. School principals provide feedback based on observed practices, data, and student outcomes. This is important because it facilitates reflective practice by encouraging teachers to assess their instructional strategies. It also provides actionable recommendations for improvement that enhance teaching effectiveness. Lastly, it supports teacher professional growth by

identifying strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for targeted reskilling or upskilling. This support transforms classroom observations into meaningful learning experiences for teachers. The relevance lies in its direct impact on teaching quality, as well as its alignment with professional development and continuous improvement goals.

Teachers value constructive feedback that identifies both strengths and areas for improvement. When administrators provide specific, evidence-based comments grounded in observed classroom practices, teachers gain clearer insight into their instructional performance. This process helps teachers recognize effective strategies they should sustain and areas that require enhancement. Feedback becomes relevant when it shifts from mere evaluation to developmental guidance. It transforms classroom observation into a supportive process that promotes growth rather than fear or compliance.

Ultimately, technical support from school administrators during classroom observations is both important and relevant because it bridges evaluation with professional growth. It ensures that teachers receive clear guidance, constructive feedback, and resources necessary to improve instructional quality. In essence, it transforms classroom observation from a mere assessment exercise into a collaborative, developmental process that uplifts teaching practices and positively impacts student learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION

This research contributes significantly to the educational landscape of the Department of Education (DepEd), specifically within the context of Panglao District, Bohol Province. Its impact extends to local schools and holds valuable insights for prospective researchers. The study employed a qualitative research method. The qualitative data set was the identification of the most challenging indicator during classroom observation as bases for reskilling and upskilling needs of teachers. Interviews provide teachers with the opportunity to explain the specific difficulties they encounter in meeting COT indicators, such as classroom management, learner engagement, and instructional strategies. Moreover, interviews enable the researcher to gather rich, detailed, and context-specific data that are essential in identifying actual skill gaps and professional development needs. This depth of information is crucial in designing a responsive reskilling and upskilling program that directly addresses teachers' real challenges. Also, it would prove to be a priceless tool in the collection of comprehensive, situation-specific data that goes beyond basic statistical analysis and contributes to a deeper comprehension of the dynamics within classroom observation. The use of interviews is considered the most appropriate and effective research method. This approach allows in-depth exploration of public elementary school teachers' lived experiences, perceptions, and challenges in Panglao district, Division of Bohol from the school year 2024-2025 related to the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) and determined the adaptive measures of those COT-based challenges and technical assistance received by teachers from school head during classroom observation.

Findings

The study revealed the following findings:

1. Teacher Profile. The teacher profile shows that most educators are in the early to mid-career stage, with the majority having 1–10 years of teaching experience, while only a few have more than 10 years. This suggests limited opportunities for mentorship from highly experienced teachers. In terms of grade level, teachers are evenly distributed across all levels, ensuring balanced and representative data and allowing professional development programs to address common instructional needs across the entire elementary level. Regarding seminars and trainings, all teachers have received foundational training in key teaching competencies, followed by upskilling in effective remediation strategies, enhancing their ability to address diverse learner needs and meet COT indicators.

2. Teacher’s COT-Based Challenges based on PPST domains. The study found that public elementary teachers face significant pedagogical challenges in implementing the Classroom Observation Tool (COT), particularly in applying higher-level and learner-centered teaching strategies. Key difficulties include integrating Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), creating interactive and student-centered classroom environments, consistently applying literacy and numeracy strategies across subjects, and implementing differentiated instruction to meet diverse learner needs. These challenges are mainly instructional rather than procedural, highlighting the need for targeted reskilling and upskilling programs to improve teaching practices, classroom performance, and overall learner outcomes.

3. Adaptive Measures of Teachers to Address the Challenges during Classroom Observation. Teachers implemented adaptive strategies to address challenges observed in integrating higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), differentiated instruction, classroom management, and literacy and numeracy approaches. These included scaffolded questioning, contextualized teaching, collaborative learning, flexible grouping, lesson plan adjustments, and improved classroom organization. They also responded to feedback from school heads through reflective practices during post-observation conferences, leading to targeted instructional improvements. Adaptive practices were further supported by technical assistance and professional development activities such as conferences, seminars, and curriculum training. Overall, these adaptive measures shifted classroom observation into a growth-oriented process, enhancing teaching practices, supporting continuous professional development, and improving student learning outcomes.

4. Technical Supports of Teachers by School Administrators/School Head in the Implementation of Classroom Observation. Technical support during classroom observations enhances teaching effectiveness, teacher confidence, and overall classroom quality. Pre-conference support helps teachers prepare effectively by clarifying

observation criteria, aligning lessons with curriculum standards, and reducing anxiety. Also, it promotes a collaborative and developmental environment, shifting teachers' perceptions of observation from evaluation to professional growth. Post-conference support is essential for reflective practice, as it provides evidence-based feedback and actionable recommendations for instructional improvement. Constructive and specific feedback enables teachers to identify strengths and areas for improvement, supporting continuous professional development. Technical support facilitates targeted reskilling and upskilling by highlighting instructional gaps and opportunities for growth.

Conclusions

The study reveals that while public elementary school teachers are competent in lesson planning, use of instructional resources, and assessment practices, they face significant challenges in meeting higher-level COT demands, particularly in promoting higher-order thinking skills. Instruction remains focused on lower-level cognitive tasks rather than critical and creative thinking. Teachers also experience difficulties in integrating literacy and numeracy across subjects, facilitating collaborative and meaningful learning environments, and addressing diverse learner needs due to constraints such as large class sizes, limited time, and inadequate resources.

Moreover, participation in mass trainings does not necessarily translate to effective classroom practice, revealing a gap between theory and implementation. In order to address these challenges, the need for a structured, responsive, and competency-based reskilling and upskilling program is essential in order to enhance instructional effectiveness, and improve learner outcomes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested for consideration based on the study's conclusions and findings:

- 1. Implement a targeted reskilling and upskilling program:** This ensures teachers gain practical skills in differentiated instruction, learner-centered strategies, and classroom management, directly addressing gaps identified in classroom observation. Hands-on training and simulations make learning more applicable and increase teacher confidence, leading to more effective lesson delivery and improved student engagement.
- 2. Strengthen mentoring and coaching systems:** Mentoring and instructional coaching provide continuous, personalized support for teachers, bridging the gap between theory and classroom practice. Collaborative lesson planning and peer guidance foster professional growth, sharing of effective strategies, and confidence in implementing new teaching approaches.
- 3. Ensure continuous monitoring and feedback:** Regular formative observations aligned with COT indicators provide teachers with evidence-based insights into their instructional performance. Constructive feedback and individualized

improvement plans help teachers reflect, refine practices, and sustain ongoing professional development.

- 4. Provide contextualized and needs-based training:** Training based on actual classroom observation results ensures relevance and addresses real instructional challenges rather than generalized topics. Needs-based approaches maximize learning outcomes, improve teacher competence, and directly impact classroom effectiveness.
- 5. Promote Professional Learning Communities:** This encourages collaboration among teachers, enabling the sharing of best practices, resources, and strategies to manage diverse learners. It fosters a supportive professional environment and strengthens overall instructional quality.
- 6. Enhance policy support and follow-through mechanisms:** Sustained technical assistance and classroom-based monitoring from educational authorities ensure that professional development initiatives are implemented effectively and maintained over time. Policy support reinforces accountability, strengthens instructional practices, and promotes long-term improvement in teaching and learning outcomes.

A structured, competency-based reskilling and upskilling program is essential to address teachers' instructional gaps. It should focus on practical strategies that enhance higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), learner engagement, and student-centered teaching. Continuous mentoring, coaching, and regular COT-aligned feedback help teachers effectively apply these strategies, improve instructional competence, and ultimately achieve better classroom performance and learner outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Consideration

The study strictly followed ethical standards to protect the rights and welfare of all participants. Permissions were obtained from school authorities, and informed consent was secured from all participants. Participation was voluntary, with the right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, and all data were used solely for academic purposes and stored securely. These measures ensured that the entire research process upheld privacy, dignity, and ethical integrity.

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